

Knowledge, Perception of Students Towards COVID-19 and its Vaccine and Practices Adopted to prevent the Spread of the Disease Among College Students

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ABSTRACT

Corona Virus Disease-19 (COVID-19) is not just an ordinary disease. It is a contagious and deadly disease that could wipe out the present generation if its spread cannot be prevented. Prevention and cure measures/programs must be implemented soonest. However, the success of these measures is dependent on the target clients' level of knowledge regarding the potency of the virus that is spreading and killing the victims and their perception of the efficacy of the vaccines in protecting people, and as well as their willingness to subject themselves before the recommended health protocols and vaccines. Thus, this study was conducted with 113 third and fourth-year students of the Western Philippines University - Quezon Campus to generate sets of information as a contribution to the pool of knowledge system regarding COVID-19, which could serve as the basis for crafting and implementing pro-people control measures. Most respondents are knowledgeable about the characteristics of the virus concerning its mode of infection and symptoms and believe that the health protocols recommended by the government could help prevent the spread of the disease. However, some are less knowledgeable that the virus could be transmitted by breathing in droplets from the infected person, that not all infected persons exhibited symptoms of the disease, and COVID-19 virus is not an airborne disease. Besides, some still believe local knowledge systems, e.g., that the virus could be prevented by drinking *calamansi* juice, which is not transmissible in hot and humid areas. Many of them rarely take vitamins to strengthen their immune system. Most respondents do not want to be vaccinated since they believe the vaccine cannot give them future insurance that they will not get infected with the virus once vaccinated. Besides, they also perceived that the current vaccine could not protect them from the new strain of coronavirus.

Keywords: *Knowledge, Perception of Students, COVID-19, Vaccine, Disease Prevention*

INTRODUCTION

Vaccination and other medical interventions cannot solely prevent the spread and contain the coronavirus, Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19), on school campuses and the immediate community (Beeraka, 2021). Appropriate knowledge, the right attitude, and practices on COVID-19 among target clients are essential considerations in developing plans and strategies for effectively controlling the disease (Yoseph et al., 2021). Emotions drive human beings. They do things (practices) based on emotions. Emotions are products of knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions (Zhang et al., 2022). Hence, assessing the levels of knowledge, attitude, and perceptions of the potential clients are important considerations in crafting workable and effective strategies and schemes for solving a problem they face.

Considering the escalating cases of COVID-19, all sectors of society must be involved in the fight against the disease. In fact, as of February 3, 2021, the total number of cases of COVID-19 in the Philippines is 528,853, with 10,874 deaths, while 487 611 recovered out of the 110,440,086 total population. Globally, there are 104,378,657 cases with total deaths of 2,262,084 and 76,227,718 recovered; and the Philippines ranks number 32 in number of cases (Buenaventura et al., 2020). The educational institution is one of the sectors of society that should be considered in our fight against COVID-19 (Izumi et al., 2021). Students could be agents in pushing back the ill effects of this pandemic on campuses, their families, and the immediate community where they live.

Students could inadvertently push and prevent the spread of the COVID-19 virus not only on school campuses but also on their families and immediate community spread or prevent the disease (Guilamo-Ramos et al., 2021). If they are not well-informed about the menace of the disease, they may unintentionally spread it to others. Nevertheless, if they are well-informed and have the right attitude towards preventing the spread of the disease, they could be potential agents in helping educate fellow students, members of their immediate family, and the community regarding how the disease could spread, be controlled, and be prevented from spreading. Assessing their level of knowledge and attitudes toward COVID-19 and ascertaining the level of adoption of the practices implemented by the government to contain the spread of the virus is essential so that the results of which can be used as a basis for the formulation of workable strategies for containing and preventing the spread of COVID-19 in campuses and in the immediate community where they are residing (Hatabu et al., 2020).

In a related development, the government is in the process of preparing the mechanisms to be adopted in vaccinating all citizens in order for them to be protected from getting infected with the deadly disease (Mascellino et al., 2021). Acceptance of the vaccine among the citizenry is an essential consideration in planning and crafting measures to prevent the spread of the disease because if many will not be amenable to being vaccinated, the effort of the government to contain such disease could be jeopardized. In a recent cross-sectional study conducted in Uganda, about 47 percent of the client-respondents perceived vaccination as risky (Echoru et al., 2020). As the prime implementer of the vaccination program, the government should look into developing vaccine acceptance strategies. However, this could be possible if we can ascertain why some do not want to get vaccinated (Schoch-Spana et al., 2021).

Thus, based on the above premises, this study was proposed to be conducted soonest so that its results could be used to formulate policies and strategies for containing and preventing the spread of this deadly disease.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study utilized a quantitative descriptive research design to assess the level of knowledge about COVID-19 and its vaccine, students' perception towards the spread and control of the disease, and their practices adopted from the guidelines provided by the government. This study used a researcher-made questionnaire to extract statistical data.

Respondents. The respondents of this study are the officially enrolled third and fourth students in education and rural development programs, Second Semester, SY 2020-2021. The research instrument was prepared and sent in Google form, which is why only the third and fourth-year students were selected as respondents since they have a virtual connection

Data Collection Procedure. Cognizant of the government's policy, which prohibits face-to-face mode of teaching and adopts asynchronous, synchronous, and modular modes of instruction in schools, the data collection needed in the study was administered virtually to the student respondents.

Data Analysis Procedure. Measures of central tendencies, ranks, totals, and averages were used to analyze and present data. The applicable statistical measure was also used for clarity of data presentation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 indicates that eight out of 10 and about six out of 10 respondents are females whose ages fell into the age bracket 21 and below. The average age across respondents is 22.51. The youngest and oldest of the respondents Out of the total targeted number of 211 respondents, 113 (54 percent) submitted back their questionnaires (Table 2). Of these 113 respondents, 65 (57.52 percent) are Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) students and 38 (33.63 percent) are Bachelor of Science in Rural Development Management (BSRDM) students (Table 3). Across program levels, 91 (80.53 percent) of them are third-year students.

As to the sex and age of the respondents, eight out of 10 are females, with an average age of 22.51 years old across all respondents (Table 1).

Table 1. Sex and age of the respondents

CRITERIA	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
❖ Sex		
Female	93	82.30
Male	20	17.70
❖ Age (in Bracket)		
21 and Below	64	56.64
22-26	34	30.08
27-32	11	9.73
33 and Above	1	0.88
Average: 22.51	Lowest: 20 years	Highest: 33 years

N=113

Table 2. Distribution of the respondents by year levels and programs

PROGRAM & YEAR LEVEL	TOTAL TARGET RESPONDENTS	NO. RESPONDING	PERCENTAGE
❖ BEED			
• Third year	82	53	25.12
• Fourth-year	28	12	5.69
❖ BSRDM			
• Third year	65	28	13.27
• Fourth-year	21	10	4.74
❖ BSED			
• Third year	15	10	4.74
• Fourth year*	0	0	0.00
Total	211	113	53.55

*no enrollee for the fourth year

Table 3. Distribution of the respondents by curricular program and year level, first semester

CRITERIA	ACADEMIC PROGRAMS						TOTAL	
	BEED		BSED*		RDM			
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Third Year	53	46.90	10	8.85	28	24.78	91	80.53
Fourth Year	12	10.62	0	0.00	10	8.85	22	19.47
Total	65	57.52	10	8.85	38	33.63	113	100.00

*no enrollee for the fourth year

Level of Knowledge on COVID-Related Issues

"Knowledge is power," as the adage says, "...means that knowledge is more powerful than physical strength and no great work can be done without knowledge. Knowledge is a powerful factor that empowers people to achieve great results. The more knowledge a person gains, the more powerful he becomes." (<http://importantindia.com>). More than that, knowledge helps us solve problems (<http://blog.udemy.com>). Thus, working knowledge among our students on the menace of COVID-19 would help us fight against the possible spread of the disease to others. The level of their working knowledge on the issues surrounding COVID-19, *ceteris paribus*, is related to how they will prevent such spread to others.

As to the knowledge of issues related to COVID-19, nine factors were included (Table 4). These include, among other things, issues about whether COVID-19 from China is contagious, its incubation period, symptoms, how the virus could be transmitted, who are prone to the disease, and health protocols. The rating scales employed for the level of knowledge are High, Middle, Low, and None.

All of the respondents are aware of the given issues as presented in Table 4, except those related to symptoms and mode of appearance of symptoms where a negligible number (2 and 1) of the respondents reported "None" (no knowledge); see Chart 1 below (of which these said data are not visibly reflected in the chart). In fact, across all respondents and issues, about 100 percent of them signified awareness of such issues, and of this, 66.47 percent reported high awareness.

As to health protocols, such as regular hand washing, social distancing, wearing a mask, and staying at home, 8 out of 10 are highly aware of them. At the same time, 7 out of 10 are highly aware of the common symptoms of the disease, and social distancing reduces the chance of spreading the disease, and older people and those with medical problems are prone to the disease. However, few of them do not know that not all infected individuals exhibit symptoms and COVID-19 virus is not an air-borne disease.

Based on this finding, it is safe to say that almost all college students know essential information related to COVID-19.

Table 4. Level of knowledge on issues related to COVID-19

CRITERIA/ISSUES	LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE & RATING (in %) n=113			
	High	Mid	Low	None
1. Regular hand washing, social distancing, avoiding crowded places, wearing masks, and staying at home can protect a person from being infected with COVID-19.	83.19	16.81	-	-
2. The most common symptoms of COVID-19 are fever, tiredness, dry cough, and body pains.	76.99	20.35	0.88	1.77
3. Social distancing from an infected person may reduce the chances of being infected.	75.22	21.24	3.54	-
4. People of old age and those with underlying medical problems like heart problems are more prone to develop serious illnesses.	73.45	21.24	5.31	-
5. One can be infected if they breathe in droplets from an infected person.	71.68	26.55	1.77	-
6. COVID-19 is a contagious disease caused by the coronavirus from China.	67.26	30.08	2.65	-
7. The incubation period of the coronavirus is 14 days.	67.26	28.32	4.42	-
8. Not all infected persons exhibit symptoms.	46.02	40.71	12.39	0.88
9. COVID-19 is not an airborne disease.	37.17	38.94	20.35	3.54
Mean	66.47	27.14	5.70	0.69

The chart below (Chart 1) indicates the relationship between the respondents' knowledge levels concerning the issues surrounding COVID-19, of which a more significant number of them are highly aware of the said issues.

Perception of the Respondents

Perception is an essential factor in human behavior. Humans act or behave the way they do as influenced by their perception of matters affecting them. A person with a positive perception or regard towards others usually behaves nicely with them. Perception is a product of a human's understanding and interpretation of phenomena, circumstances, or an object. It is directly related to the kinds of our

exhibited behavior. For instance, a perception that COVID-19 is contagious and deadly might influence people to act to protect themselves from possible transmission of the disease.

Table 5 presents the respondents' perceptions of 13 assumptions surrounding COVID-19. These are related to the potential of health protocols in preventing or minimizing the spread of the disease and notions which people tried to consider in possibly preventing and curing the said disease.

All the respondents agreed that regular washing of hands helps protect from getting infected with the virus. Of all of them, 7 out of 10 indicated that they strongly agreed that regular hand washing is a good practice in preventing oneself from getting infected by the virus. This is also true concerning social distancing, wearing a face mask, and staying at home. However, few respondents do not agree that hand sanitizing while shopping in marketplaces and covering the mouth and nose when sneezing and coughing help prevent the virus's possible spread

However, it was interesting to note that many respondents agreed that drinking *calamansi* juice can help prevent COVID infection. At the same time, vaccines for pneumonia and antibiotic medicines could also effectively control the disease. Some also believed the notion that hot baths could kill coronavirus.

As to the mode of transmission, some believe that coronavirus cannot be transmitted in hot and humid climates (8 out of 10 of them); but can be transmitted through mosquito bites (6 out of 10 of them).

One-third of the respondents believed COVID medicines were already available in drug stores.

Table 5. Perception of the respondents relative to COVID-19 issues

PERCEPTION	RESPONSE* (n=113)		
	SA	A	D
❖ Washing your hands regularly helps protect you from getting infected with COVID-19.	66.37	33.63	-
❖ Observing social distancing when in the marketplace and department stores should be strictly observed.	65.49	34.5	-
❖ Staying at home all the time helps protect against possible COVID infections.	60.18	39.82	-
❖ Always wearing your mask when you leave your residence helps you not be infected with COVID-19.	57.22	41.59	0.88
❖ Sanitizing your hands often when shopping or visiting places helps you not be infected with COVID-19.	55.75	40.70	3.54
❖ Covering your mouth and nose when you cough or sneeze helps prevent the possible spread of COVID-19.	53.10	38.04	8.84
1. Hot baths cannot prevent coronavirus.	22.12	57.52	20.35
2. COVID-19 virus cannot be transmitted in hot and humid places.	15.93	65.49	18.58
❖ Drinking <i>Calamansi</i> juice controlled COVID-19.	15.04	58.40	26.54
3. Coronavirus can also be transmitted through mosquito bites.	8.84	48.67	42.47
4. Vaccines against pneumonia can also protect against COVID-19.	5.30	56.63	38.05
5. Antibiotics are effective in protecting against COVID-19.	1.77	61.06	37.17
❖ Medicine that can cure COVID-19 is already available in drugstores.	1.77	34.50	68.14
Mean	33.00	47.04	20.00
* SA = Strongly Agree A = Agree D = Disagree			

Frequency of Practicing Precautionary Measures

The degree of practicing or taking precautionary measures to avoid possible COVID-19 infection is related to the level of knowledge regarding the ill effects of the disease on one's health. In Table 4, we know that the respondents have a high level of knowledge of how coronavirus is transmitted and how to minimize the possibility of getting infected. In contrast, Table 5 indicated that, generally speaking, most agreed that precautionary health protocols could help minimize the spread of the virus. Table 6, on the other hand, shows the frequency of practicing the health protocols they are aware of to prevent the virus from getting infected.

Wearing of Face Mask. The facemask is essential in the prevention of getting infected with coronavirus as it would serve as a "... simple barrier to help prevent your respiratory droplets from reaching others. Studies show that masks reduce the spray of droplets when worn over the nose and mouth." (cdc.gov (2021)). Wearing of facemask is recommended to everyone, even if one does not feel sick, especially in public places. As to the study's findings, 9 out of 10 (86.72 percent) respondents reported that they always wear face masks; the rest wear their facemasks most of the time (Table 6). This clearly shows that all of them have internalized the value and importance of wearing masks to prevent getting infected with the virus.

Covering the Mouth. All respondents claimed they covered their mouths when coughing or sneezing. 7 out of 10 (68.14 percent) did it always when coughing and sneezing, while 3 out of 10 did it most of the time. However, seven of them (6.19 percent) just rarely did it. Though this number is few compared to the rest, this is something to be considered in implementing precautionary health protocols because they would be potential transmitters of the disease if they got infected with the virus.

Hand Washing. Hand washing with soap and water is considered one of the best methods to prevent getting infected with the virus. The WHO reported that "Frequent and proper hand hygiene is one of the most important measures that can be used to prevent infection with the COVID-19 virus" (WHO, 2020). It not only reduces the possible spread of the coronavirus but also prevents the spread of other viral illnesses. As to the study results, all reported they were doing hand washing. However, six of them (5.31 percent) do hand washing rarely.

Hand Sanitizer. Although hand washing using soap and water is considered to be one of the best ways to control the spread and getting of infected coronavirus, using hand sanitizer (containing between 60-95% alcohol) may help get rid of unwanted germs in one's hands if water and soap are not available. And, for just sharing information, frequent use of hand sanitizers makes one's hands very dry (familydoctor.org).

Table 6 shows that 5 and 4 out of 10 among the respondents **always** and **most of the time** use hand sanitizers when they are going to public places, respectively. The rest are using hand sanitizer infrequently.

Staying at Home. Staying at home and/or home quarantine is one of the recommended health protocols to prevent the spread of the coronavirus because it is one way of avoiding contact with the virus, which infected people might have coughed and sneezed out through droplets. Coronavirus "...can live on different surfaces for up to 3 days." (Wray, 2021). Thus, any contact with virus surfaces may infect the concerned individual. The best way to avoid such contact is to stay at home. Concerning the study's findings, most (50.98 percent) of the respondents stayed home during this pandemic, while 4 out of 10 stayed home most of the time. Nobody reported that they went out but stayed at home, especially during this study.

Social Distancing. Social distancing is also called physical distancing. It is one of the ways to retarding the spread of coronavirus to other people. Moosa (2020) describes it as "... a set of non-pharmaceutical interventions or measures taken to prevent the spread of a contagious disease by maintaining physical distance between people and reducing the number of times they come into close contact with each other. It involves a variety of measures, including school closures, workplace closures, cancellation of mass gatherings (such as sporting events, concerts, and political rallies), travel restrictions, shielding (limiting face-to-face contacts, conducting business by phone or online, avoiding public places and reducing unnecessary travel), quarantine, cordon sanitaire (isolating burial and treatment zones from the general population), and protective sequestration (barricading highways and putting arriving train passengers in quarantine)."

The study results show that all respondents observed the 3-feet social distancing when they went out into public places. However, more than half of them (the majority) do not always observe such health protocol, and 15 out of 113 observed it rarely. A study is also needed to determine why not all observed proper physical distancing in public places.

Taking Vitamins. Vitamins can increase the general condition of an individual as they strengthen one's immune system. Cheriyeath (2021) reported that a "...balanced diet that includes vitamins A, B, C, D, E, and K, and micronutrients such as sodium, zinc, potassium, chloride, calcium,

and phosphorus might help maintain general wellbeing and strengthen the immune system, thus decreasing infections. A deficiency of vitamins and minerals in the plasma leads to sub-par immune system performance, leading to a poor immune state." However, based on the study, many just take it rarely; 12 out of 113 (10.62 percent) do not take over-the-counter vitamins. The possible reason for this could be the additional cost they might incur to buy vitamins.

In Chart 2, it is noticeable that the frequency of practicing health measures diminishes from the use of facemasks down to taking vitamins. Wearing facemasks is **always** practiced by most of them, while social distancing and taking supplemental vitamins is **less** practiced. A further study could be done to explain this phenomenon.

Table 6. Frequency of practicing COVID-19 precautionary measures

PRACTICES	ANSWER* (n=113)			
	A	M	S	NP
1. Wearing a mask when going out from home to public places	86.72	13.27	-	-
2. Covering mouth and nose when coughing or sneezing	68.14	25.66	6.19	-
3. Regularly washing your hands	58.41	36.28	5.31	-
4. Using hand sanitizer most often when going out in public places	53.10	38.05	8.85	-
5. Staying at home during this COVID-19 pandemic	50.98	41.59	7.96	-
6. Observing/following the 3-feet social distancing when going out in crowded places and meeting people	35.40	51.33	13.27	-
7. Taking vitamins in boosting the immune system	25.66	32.74	30.97	10.62
Mean	54.06	34.13	10.36	1.52

* A = Always; M = Most of the time; S = Sometimes; NP = Not Practicing

Perception on Vaccination

Perception plays a significant role in the choices individuals make. It affects decision-making as they make decisions based on their perceptions (bartleby.com; csus.edu). In the case of vaccination against COVID-19, people's decisions might be affected by their perception of such vaccination. If they think, for example, that getting vaccinated will endanger their lives, they simply will not subject themselves to vaccination.

The study's results regarding the respondents' perceptions of vaccination are presented in Table 7. Four evaluative questions were put forward to elicit their perceptions regarding vaccination. Regarding willingness to submit for vaccination, 8 out of 10 (78.76 percent) respondents do not want to get the vaccination. Moreover, 7 out of 10 (69.01 percent) believed vaccinated individuals could still get infected by the coronavirus.

It was also interesting to note that about 7 out of 10 respondents believed that the current vaccine provided by the government could not protect vaccinated individuals from getting infected with the new strain of the virus. Besides, about three-fourths (72.57 percent) of the respondents believed that under this pandemic, it is better to develop and produce a medicine that could cure the disease rather than produce a vaccine. This notion could be attributed to the fact that every time people get sick, their physicians give them prescriptions, and get healed by taking the prescribed medicines. Besides, they may be aware that developing a reliable and effective vaccine takes years.

A further study could unearth why many don't want to be vaccinated, why they thought vaccinated individuals could still be infected with the virus, and that the existing vaccines provided by the government could not prevent further infection from another variant or strain a commendable research activity.

Table 7. Perceptions on vaccination

QUESTIONS	YES		NO	
	No.	%	No.	%
➤ Are you willing to be vaccinated against COVID-19 when the vaccine is already available?	24	21.23	89	78.76
➤ Do you think being vaccinated can prevent you from being infected with COVID-19?	35	30.97	78	69.01
➤ Do you think the present vaccine to be distributed by the government could also protect you from the new strain of COVID-19?	38	33.63	75	66.37
➤ Do you think developing a medicine to cure COVID-19 is more practical than developing a vaccine?	82	72.57	31	27.43
Mean	45	39.82	68	60.18

N=113

CONCLUSION

Based on the salient findings of the study, the following conclusions could be drawn out:

1. Many of the respondents are aware of how the virus could be transmitted and understand the symptoms associated with it.
2. Many believed that basic health protocols recommended by the government could prevent the possible spread of the disease.
3. Some still trust local knowledge and practices to prevent themselves from getting infected with the virus, such as hot baths and drinking *calamansi* juice.
4. All of the respondents wear masks regularly and most of the time; however, some rarely observe proper social distancing, using hand sanitizer when going to public places, and covering their mouth and nose when coughing and sneezing.

Most of them don't want to get vaccinated as it would not ensure them not to be infected with the virus anymore. Besides, they also believed that the current vaccines distributed by the government could not prevent them from being infected with a new strain of coronavirus.

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